

Temperature Behavior of AlGaIn/GaN on SiC HEMTs

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Abstract — This study presents extensive characterization and comparison of current GaN/SiC devices (from 5 US manufacturers) across temperature (−25 — 125°C). The changes with temperature for: saturated current (I_{dss}), transconductance (g_m), and maximum stable gain (MSG) are measured and statistics are studied. The typical temperature-coefficients (TC) are established for I_{dss} , g_m , and MSG in GaN technology. This information is useful for MMIC designs. The minimum temperature coefficients compare well with theoretical expectations. Finally, a correlation is observed between the temperature behavior of RF and DC parameters.

I. INTRODUCTION

The reliability and performance of HEMTs and MMICs depend critically on the device's operating channel temperature [1]. Devices based on wide band gap materials (such as GaN, SiC) promise much higher power densities and potential for higher temperature operation than GaAs, Si, and SiGe devices [2]. This study presents extensive characterization and comparison of current GaN/SiC devices from many manufacturers across temperature (−25 — 125°C).

II. MEASURED RESULTS

To quantize the effect of temperature on the performance of GaN/SiC device, a set of current AlGaIn/GaN pHEMT devices were characterized at −25, 25, 75, and 125°C base plate (on-wafer chuck). At each temperature, the DC IV curves were measured and I_{dss} recorded. In addition, the on-wafer S-parameters were measured at $V_d = 20V$ and a fixed drain current (equal to 50% of the room-temperature I_{dss}). The dissipated DC power is fixed and hence the channel temperature to the chuck temperature should be constant (assuming GaN and SiC have linear thermal conductivities over the −25 — 125°C temperature range). The gate lengths (L_g) for the HEMTs were between 0.2 – 0.4 μm . Of most interest to MMIC designers is g_m , which is frequency independent, and maximum stable gain (MSG) which is a two-port invariant quantity. The RF g_m is a fundamental measure of the device's performance and is closely related to L_g and the electron saturation velocity (v_s). It can be extracted from the low-frequency S_{21} data using the equation [3]:

$$S_{21} = -2 \cdot g_m \cdot Z_0 \quad (1)$$

where Z_0 is the characteristic impedance of the measurement system. The extracted values of g_m were verified by deriving small-signal models and comparing

with Eq. (1). In addition, $f_t = g_m / 2 \pi (C_{gs} + C_{gd}) = v_s / 2 \pi L_g$ [4] and

$$g_m = \frac{v_s (C_{gs} + C_{gd})}{L_g} \quad (2)$$

The MSG determines the gain limitations of the device and is the two-port invariant quantity that is not affected by input and output parasitics [6]. MSG is calculated using $MSG = |S_{21}/S_{12}|$. As an example, the measured MSG over temperature for one of the devices is plotted on Fig. 1. The measured $\Delta MSG (=MSG^T - MSG^{25^\circ C})$ and $\Delta S_{21} (=S_{21}^T - S_{21}^{25^\circ C})$ of the HEMT in Fig. 1 are shown in Figs. 2, and 3. Except at low frequencies, ΔMSG is essentially constant across frequency, unlike changes in ΔS_{21} . This has been observed for all of the measured devices.

The temperature behavior of different HEMTs is plotted on Figs. 4, 5, and 6 for I_{dss} , g_m , and ΔMSG . In all cases the measured quantity was scaled to a 1mm gate width for comparison of different device sizes. Table 1 summarizes the results of all the HEMTs giving the temperature coefficient defined as $TC(x) = (\Delta x/x)/\Delta T$.

Fig. 1 MSG for four measured temperatures.

Fig. 2 Change in MSG ($MSG^T - MSG^{25^\circ C}$) from room temperature value.

Fig. 3 Change in S21 ($S21^T - S21^{25^\circ C}$) from room temperature value.

Fig. 4 Plot of I_{dss} vs. base plate temperature.

Fig. 5 Plot of g_m vs. base plate temperature.

Fig. 6 Plot of $\Delta MSG (=MSG^T - MSG^{25^\circ C})$ in dB vs. chuck temperature.

II. DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

The measured results contain a number of findings. In particular, the following may be noted:

- Eq. (2) indicates that $TC(g_m) = TC(v_s) + TC(C_{gs} + C_{gd})$. Monte-Carlo simulations of GaN [5] predict $TC(v_s) = -700 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$, Fig. 7(a). The minimum $TC(g_m)$ observed is $-830 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ which is larger than $TC(v_s)$. We can attribute $-700 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ to v_s 's reduction with temperature and $-130 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ to $(C_{gs} + C_{gd})$. In all the measured cases, the change in $(C_{gs} + C_{gd})$ had the same sign as changes in v_s thus increasing $TC(g_m)$. On the average, $TC(g_m) = -1870 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ with $-700 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ attributable to v_s and $-1170 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ attributable to $(C_{gs} + C_{gd})$.

- Fig. 8 shows a plot of $TC(g_m)$ and $TC(MSG)$, both are RF parameters, vs. $TC(I_{dss})$, a DC parameter. A correlation is observed indicating that temperature coefficients for RF parameters can be estimated by measuring DC changes in I_{dss} with temperature. The proportionality of $TC(g_m)$ and $TC(MSG)$ to $TC(I_{dss})$ is approximately 1. The minimum observed $TC(I_{dss})$ and $TC(MSG)$ were greater than $-700 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$, the $TC(v_s)$ change.
- For MMIC design purposes the results indicate that on average $\Delta MSG/\Delta T$ has a range of -0.01 to $-0.03 \text{ dB}/^\circ\text{C}$ and $\Delta I_{dss} / I_{dss} \Delta T$ has a range of -1200 to $-2000 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$.
- For comparison, a high performance NEC GaAs $0.2\mu\text{m}$ pHEMT was measured. The data is shown on Fig. 9. The observed $TC(g_m)$ is $-2000 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ (less than GaAs's predicted $TC(v_s)$ of $-1700 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ from Fig. 7(b)).

Fig. 8 Correlation of RF parameters Δg_m and ΔMSG with DC parameter ΔI_{dss}

Fig. 7 Monte-Carlo calculation of maximum drift velocity (diamonds), saturated drift velocity (circles), and mobility across temperature for (a) GaN and (b) GaAs (Ref. [5]).

Fig. 9 Transconductance (g_m) and saturated current (I_{dss}) change with temperature for a GaAs pHEMT.

Temp. Coeff.	Units	Mean	Std Dev.	Min.	Max.
$\Delta\text{MSG} / \text{MSG} \Delta T$	$10^3 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$	-1.71	0.73	-0.93	-3.18
$\Delta I_{\text{dss}} / I_{\text{dss}} \Delta T$	$10^3 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$	-1.67	0.44	-1.01	-2.59
$\Delta g_m / g_m \Delta T$	$10^3 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$	-1.87	0.80	-0.83	-2.92

Table 1. Statistics of Temperature Coefficient for all measured devices.

II. CONCLUSION

From the preceding measurements, the following is concluded:

1. GaN's degradation of performance with temperature is less than GaAs's due to GaN's reduced v_s variation of with temperature.
2. The temperature behavior of RF quantities (such as g_m and MSG) can be estimated from that of DC quantities (such I_{dss}).
3. The average $\Delta\text{MSG}/\Delta T$ value is $-0.02 \text{ dB}/^\circ\text{C}$ and the average $\Delta I_{\text{dss}} / I_{\text{dss}} \Delta T$ value is $-1600 \text{ ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$.

Temperature effects on breakdown voltage, pinch-off voltage merit further investigation.

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